

1 **MBD3 transition complex assembly during transformation and in neoplasia.**

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6 We used measurement of whole transcription in hyperplasia, intraepithelial neoplasia and in situ
7 carcinoma for discovery of epigenetic control of transformation. We describe here MBD3 family activation
8 in cancer. Importantly, we demonstrate convincingly that the MBD3-like gene, MBD3L2, is induced during
9 oncogenesis associated with DuxAP factor activity, a correlate of or proximally related event to induction of
10 ECT2 during transformation. MBD3 is activated in cancer and MBD3L2 is a reliable marker of a novel
11 oncogene transition state in transformation of human cells.

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